

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN A MULTICULTURAL SPACE

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Abstract. *In recent years, the matter of learning Russian language in a poly-cultural environment has become a main focus of many researchers. The article deals with the issue of multilateral approaches to the instruction of Russian language.*

Key words: *Russian language, multi-ethnic school, multilingualism, linguistic and ethnic culture.*

Аннотация: *В последние годы проблема освоения русского языка в поликультурной среде находится в центре внимания многих исследователей. В статье рассматриваются многосторонние подходы к проблеме изучения языковых контактов.*

Ключевые слова: *русский язык, полиэтническая школа, многоязычие, лингво и этнокультура.*

Аннотация: *Сўнги йилларда рус тилини кўп маданиятли муҳитда ўзлаштириши муаммоси тадқиқотчиларнинг диққат марказида бўлиб келмоқда. Мақолада рус тилини ўрганиши жараёнида турли ёндашувларнинг роли ва аҳамияти муҳокама қилинади.*

Калит сўзлар: *рус тили, полиэтник мактаб, кўп тиллилик, лингво ва этномаданият.*

Today in the globalized world schools have become the most effective instrument for achieving the formation of a culture of interethnic relations. On the basis of this fact, we claim that the matter of teaching Russian language in a multinational school has both educational and social significance [1, 76].

Uzbekistan is a multicultural community of a special type, where typological features of the Russian and Uzbek mentality coexist in the complex unity of interpenetration and mutual influence [7, 102].

A pedagogue of the Russian language of a multiethnic school, contacting children of different nationalities, inevitably comes to the understanding that a nationally special identity, mastered by another culture, gives a clear idea of polyethnicity and linguistic diversity even in a small educational space [6,18-19]

Russian teachers of multi-ethnic schools enrich their cultural competences through the use of sociocultural approaches to teaching in their professional activities, along with communicative ones. The sociocultural approach to teaching the Russian language is also important in the educational aspect. Great attention is paid to identifying the common moral interests of multilingual peoples; for this, Russian teachers of polyethnic schools use the social experience of their learners. A good beneficial and productive factor for learners of multilingual schools is considered the frequent and constant impact on the learners of Russian environment and their inclusion in continuous language practice. The work of Russian teachers at multiethnic schools, in comparison with the activities of teachers with mono-ethnic contingent, has a number of its own characteristics, specific features, determined, first of all, by polyethnicity and multiculturalism as well as zero preparation of learners of Russian language [5, 324]. Below you may find out the main characteristics of the activity of Russian teachers of multi-ethnic schools, which distinct from the activity of teachers who instruct Russian and literature:

1. profound knowledge on methodology, which entails the need to change approaches and forms of teaching while improving teachers' methodological competences;
2. the culturological orientation of all pedagogical activities, as well as the selection of didactic material require taking into account not only the foreign language, but also its gender and age characteristics, and many other social and regional factors in the work of multiethnic schools;

3. the work and time of Russian teachers spent in the process of preparing for classes, is multi-volume and meaningful.

In the conditions of a multilingual and multi-level school community, a modern teacher of the Russian language faces with the need to combine the methods of Russian as a non-native language and Russian as a native language in the educational process [2, 98]. The main differences in the principle of presentation of language and content for Russian teachers are as follows:

1. For learners of Russian-language schools, the formation of literacy is carried out on the basis of existing speech competences and generalization of models; awareness of the language system occurs through the decomposition of the integrally perceived units of the language such as words, phrases, sentences etc. In teaching, everything should be organized under the principle from general to specific; communicative competence is formed through the development of different functional varieties of language and various genres of speech. For learners whose communicative competence and literacy do not meet the requirements of the program (educational standard), it is necessary to introduce extra courses [4, 64]. At the same time, the methodology puts the learner in front of the fact to carry out volitional, logical actions and rules, language structures remain in the form of formal schemes and operations that are stored in the memory of learners for a short period of time.

2. The primary goal in teaching bilingual students is the formation and improvement of their communicative competences based on an in-depth study of grammatical models of the Russian language. Speech developing content is mastered as a general integral material, not in parts. An analytical approach to the knowledge of language units is possible only at a very good level of knowledge of the language. Mastering the theory is limited to the concepts of “part of a word” (not a morpheme), “part of speech”, “part of a sentence.” The basic principle of teaching is teaching from specific to more general.

The experience of working in bilingual and multilingual school communities and checking process of the methodological developments in practice showed that

the points of contact of these different methods are in the field of extra courses for weak and unsuccessful Russian-speaking learners within which language models and structures are constantly revised. The effectiveness of such courses depends on the use of modern teaching technologies [3, 98]. The mastery by learners of the lexical, phonetic, grammatical phenomena of the language system should be accompanied by somatic sensations e.g., seeing, hearing, feeling, etc.). Also, in Russian classes, it is important to select such tasks that can be completed by the whole class or a group of students. Moreover, it is useful to use various language related games in Russian lessons.

It would be effective if there was a combination deductive and inductive approach in the process of teaching Russian, which allows learners working with spoken and written texts, functional varieties, and styles. In Russian classes with a multi-lingual and multi-level school community, such an organization is possible when working with texts rich in grammatical material in accordance with the aims and objectives of a particular lesson. This allows Russian teachers to solve a complex of methodological problems during the lesson: to work out spelling, punctuation and grammatical models of the language; conduct lexical and word-formation work; analyze the structure and content of the texts, and then reproduce some of their fragments. When performing different types of assignments and tasks, students often refer to the text, thus memorizing the lexical and grammatical means of the language used in it. The content of the texts must comply with the following principles:

- 1) establishment of correlative and intercultural relations;
- 2) reflection of the linguistic and ethno-cultural specifics of the Russian language;
- 3) frequent repetition of linguistic facts.

It is necessary to work on the skills of learners to create an associative field (in comparison with the native language) and discover different linguistic patterns. This process becomes more interesting and engaging if language instructors include

non-linguistic associations such as various movements, facial expressions, gestures, sound etc.

Thus, introducing the means of another language in the classroom of the Russian language has the following goals:

- the formation of students' linguistic thinking, showing the diversity of languages and the importance of any language foster students' tolerance;
- drawing students' attention to the variety of ways of expressing one idea and its meaning in different languages;
- showing students the presence or absence of the corresponding language equivalents.

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